

Functional Remission and Diagnostic Overshadowing in Early Regressive Autism: A Longitudinal Case Study Following a Naturopathic Intervention

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Abstract

Introduction: Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by marked etiological and clinical heterogeneity. In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the need to investigate integrative approaches that consider its potential multisystem nature. From the perspective of complex systems theory, effective interventions should necessarily be multidimensional and adaptive.

Case Presentation: An 18-month-old boy of Mexican nationality was evaluated for early socio-communicative regression. Independent external assessments identified a clinical suspicion of ASD and a significant global developmental delay (Battelle Developmental Quotient: 69).

Intervention: An individualized Complex Naturopathic Intervention (CNI) was implemented over 24 months. In accordance with minimal intervention protocols due to the patient's young age, it was progressively structured into three core components: (1) trophology and strict dietary exclusion (month 0); (2) ongoing parental coaching; and (3) individualized naturopathic supplementation, introduced following laboratory confirmation at month 13.

Results: A reduction in symptom severity was observed (ATEC baseline score of 56, decreasing to 10 after 24 months of intervention). The participant experienced an episode of acute regression at 5 years of age, triggered by the discontinuation of immunonutrition guidelines

(trophology), which fully remitted within 4 months following reinstatement of the intervention. External reassessments revealed methodological discrepancies: a blinded clinical evaluation at 5 years of age identified only ADHD, without detecting the autistic phenotype, with above-average cognitive performance (Full-Scale IQ: 113), whereas a final non-blinded evaluation at 7 years of age established a diagnosis of ASD level 1 with co-occurring ADHD.

Conclusions: The early application of the CNI was associated with a profound reorganization of the system, in line with complex systems models, and consistent with functional remission (optimal outcome), transitioning toward residual high-functioning neurodivergence. The case suggests a functional association between biological determinants of behavior (gut–brain axis) and illustrates successful mechanisms of functional masking, documenting a phenomenon of diagnostic overshadowing conditioned by evaluator blinding.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder, functional remission, diagnostic overshadowing, naturopathic intervention, case study

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition with heterogeneous etiology. [1–3] International guidelines recognize the need to investigate multimodal interventions that address its potential multisystem involvement. [4–6] In this context, an individualized complex naturopathic intervention (hereafter, CNI) was implemented, protocolized under the designation Katia Dolle Method® (hereafter, KDM). This CNI targets interrelated biological imbalances associated with behavioral disturbances through strategies including immunonutrition, supplementation, and structured parental support, aimed at modulating immunological, neuroendocrine, and behavioral axes. This report documents the longitudinal evolution of a case involving an 18-month-old boy who received this CNI,

evaluating the impact of modulating underlying biological factors on the severity of his initial diagnosis.

Case Presentation

Following an apparently typical early development, the participant, of Mexican nationality, experienced progressive socio-communicative regression between 10 and 15 months of age, characterized by the loss of prelinguistic skills and social gestures. At 18 months of age (March 2020), independent external assessments documented a significant delay across multiple neurodevelopmental domains and identified a clinical suspicion of ASD (Table 1). Given the regressive clinical presentation and the child’s high susceptibility to infections, the family initiated the CNI as the sole intervention (no concurrent interventions were implemented).

Considering the participant’s young age (18 months), the first phase of the intervention (from month 0 to month 12) focused exclusively on the modulation of the gastrointestinal and behavioral ecosystem through trophology and parental coaching, deferring biological testing. Subsequently, at 2 years and 6 months of age (month 13 of intervention, March–April 2021), a biological evaluation was conducted using metabolic, immunological, and microbiological profiles, which justified the introduction of the naturopathic supplementation phase. Baseline anamnestic data and biological findings are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1

Initial Diagnostic Assessment

Assessment	Result	Interpretation
M-CHAT / VEANME / CARS	Failure in 12 M-CHAT items (5 critical) VEANME: 20 points (above clinical cutoff) CARS: abnormal social relationships and imitation	Behaviors and warning signs consistent with suspected ASD
Battelle-2	Total Quotient: 69 (significant delay) Communication: 55 (severe impairment) Motor skills: 92 (preserved)	Developmental asymmetry (communicative collapse with preserved motor function)

Assessment	Result	Interpretation
Clinical observation and DSM-5	Absence of response to name and pointing Use of the adult as an instrument Hand flapping and atypical visual interest Deficit in joint attention	Probable F84.0 (ASD); indication for intensive intervention

Note. M-CHAT: Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers; BATTELLE-2: Battelle Developmental Inventory, Second Edition; VEANME: Mexican Autism Spectrum Assessment Scale; CARS: Childhood Autism Rating Scale; DSM-5: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition.

Table 2

Baseline Clinical and Biological Findings

Category	Findings
Parent-reported behavioral characteristics	Neurodevelopmental regression with loss of previously acquired communicative and social skills; absence of response to name; deficit in nonverbal communication (absence of pointing, instrumental use of the adult); intermittent and selective eye contact; atypical social preference (peer avoidance); repetitive behaviors (hand flapping) and restricted interests (fixation on circular shapes and screens); low frustration tolerance with associated tantrums
Urinary analysis	Elevated metals: As, Cs, Pb Reduced minerals: Ca
Fecal microbiology	Intestinal dysbiosis with altered commensal flora (absence of <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.) and presence of potentially pathogenic genera (<i>Citrobacter</i> , <i>Klebsiella</i>), as well as yeasts
Blood biochemistry	Dopamine: <10 pg/mL; serotonin: 214.39 ng/mL; cortisol: 10.6 µg/dL

Note. As: arsenic; Cs: cesio; Pb: lead; Ca: calcium.

Intervention

A multimodal and individualized CNI (KDM) was implemented over 24 months of active intervention (2020–2022). The reported functional changes correspond to 24 net months of effective CNI, which was structured into three core components:

(1) trophology: the elimination and substitution of foods that trigger delayed hypersensitivity reactions, aimed at reducing inflammatory cytokine cascades and correcting dysbiosis.

(2) naturopathic supplementation: a sequential and rotational regimen, organized into bimonthly blocks and reassessed every six months through laboratory testing, aimed at immunological, neurological, and neuroendocrine modulation, as well as detoxification processes.

(3) parental coaching: training in health-related care, behavioral management, and structured neurocognitive stimulation in the home setting (language, motor skills, and social abilities).

Biological evaluations were deferred until month 13 of follow-up in accordance with minimal intervention protocols, with analyses subsequently performed in independent external laboratories.

Continuous follow-up was carried out remotely, with no adverse effects reported throughout the intervention.

After achieving early functional remission milestones, naturopathic supplementation was discontinued, and a strict trophological regimen was maintained as the primary long-term strategy. However, an acute clinical fluctuation was observed at the end of 2023, triggered by reduced adherence to immunonutrition. This episode was resolved through a 4-month naturopathic intervention (March to July 2024), with no adverse effects associated with the intervention.

Follow-up and Outcomes

Psychometric assessments, laboratory analyses, and parent-reported data collected periodically throughout longitudinal follow-up documented the participant's developmental trajectory and functional changes (Tables 3 and 4, Figure 1). Laboratory analyses at month 13 of the CNI documented altered metabolic and intestinal markers (metal excretion, dysbiosis, and

catecholamine dysregulation), which justified the initiation of naturopathic supplementation at that stage.

Table 3

Longitudinal Evolution of Psychometric and Biological Parameters

Date	Assessment	Results
March 2020 (18 months of age); baseline	ATEC	Total score: 56 (moderate range)
September 2020 (24 months of age); month 6 of CNI	ATEC	Total score: 47 (mild-to-moderate range)
March 2021 (2 years and 4 months of age); month 13 of CNI	ATEC	Total score: 18 (mild range)
Marzo 2021 (2 años y 4 meses de edad); mes 13 de ICN	Laboratory analyses (urine, fecal microbiology, blood biochemistry)	Elevated metals, essential mineral deficiencies, intestinal dysbiosis, and alterations in neurotransmitter parameters (see Table 2)
March 2022 (3 years and 6 months of age); month 24 of CNI	ATEC	Total score: 10 (mild/subclinical range)

Note. ATEC: Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist.

Table 4

Longitudinal Evolution of Qualitative Clinical Milestones Reported by Caregivers

Fecha	Parent-reported observations
March 2020 (18 months of age); baseline	Biological: watery, foul-smelling stools; recurrent respiratory infections; frequent use of antibiotics Sociocommunicative: neurodevelopmental regression (loss of babbling at 14 months); absence of response to name and selective eye contact Behavioral: low frustration tolerance; visual hyperfocus (screens) and hand flapping in response to excitement

Fecha	Parent-reported observations
February 2021 (2 years and 4 months of age); month 12 of CNI	Biological: remission of infectious susceptibility; normalization of altered gastrointestinal pattern Sociocommunicative: restoration of joint attention and eye contact; recovery of pointing and production of isolated functional words Behavioral: marked reduction in tantrums; emergence of functional and early symbolic play (“playing doctor”); proactive interaction with peers

Nota. Clinical milestones were reported by caregivers during follow-up, based on non-standardized observational records, and reflect perceived functional changes in the child’s daily environment.

Neuropsychological Metrics

Longitudinal psychometric assessment demonstrated a reduction in the evaluated symptomatology (Figure 1, Table 3). Using the ATEC questionnaire, symptom severity showed a progressive decrease, from a baseline score of 56 in March 2020 to 18 points at month 12 of the intervention (February 2021), reaching 10 points at month 24 (March 2022). This reduction represents a transition from a moderate severity range to a subclinical range, suggesting a clinically significant change in symptom burden.

Figure 1. Longitudinal evolution of ATEC scores throughout follow-up

Nota. The graph illustrates a progressive reduction in symptom severity, with subsequent consolidation following the introduction of naturopathic supplementation at month 13, reaching a subclinical range (10 points) at the end of the active phase of the CNI (month 24).

External Neuropsychological Reassessments and Clinical Fluctuation.

Throughout follow-up, after completion of the initial naturopathic supplementation at 24 months (March 2022), the participant maintained clinical and behavioral stability for one uninterrupted year, relying exclusively on adherence to the trophological regimen. However, at 5 years of age (October–December 2023), the developmental trajectory showed a clinical fluctuation. According to family reports, this period of instability coincided with a systematic relaxation in adherence to the previously prescribed strict trophological modifications. During this period, the participant experienced an acute behavioral regression.

Coinciding with this episode, external reassessment A was conducted under blinded clinical conditions. This evaluation documented a Full-Scale IQ of 113, with percentiles above 90 in inattention and hyperactivity, and concluded a suspicion of ADHD and regulatory difficulties, without detecting the underlying autistic phenotype.

In response to this regression, induced by underlying biological alterations, the CNI was reinstated in March 2024, with strict adherence to the trophological regimen. After 4 months of intervention (March to July 2024), remission of the acute symptomatology was observed.

Subsequently, external reassessment B, conducted at 7 years of age (December 2025–February 2026) under non-blinded conditions (with full knowledge of the longitudinal clinical trajectory and early diagnosis), reported a General Intelligence Index of 91 (RIAS) and a Nonverbal Index of 97 (TONI-4). The MOXO continuous performance test and the BRIEF-2 scale demonstrated clinically significant impairments in sustained attention, inhibitory control, and emotional regulation. In the ASD-specific assessment, scores above the cutoff were recorded on the Autism

Spectrum Quotient (AQ = 72) and the GARS-3S scale (index 81, very high probability), whereas the Social Communication Questionnaire (SCQ) yielded a score of 10 (below the clinical threshold), and the RBS-R scale indicated mild severity in repetitive behaviors. The final diagnostic conclusion of the evaluating center determined the presence of ASD level 1, ADHD, and significant difficulties in sensory processing (Table 5).

Table 5

Comparison of External Neuropsychological Reassessments

Assessment	Methodology	Instruments and Tests	Key Results and Scores	Diagnostic Conclusion
Reassessment A at 5 years of age (October–December 2023)	Blinded (no prior diagnostic information)	WPPSI-III; ADHD-5; Sensory Profile-2	Full-Scale IQ: 113 (Verbal IQ: 106; Performance IQ: 116); ADHD-5 scale: percentiles >90 in inattention and hyperactivity; Sensory Profile-2: significantly elevated scores in avoidance and registration quadrants	Suspicion of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD); emotional regulation difficulties and cognitive inflexibility
Reassessment B at 7 years of age (December 2025–February 2026)	Non-blinded (with prior diagnostic knowledge)	RIAS; TONI-4; MOXO d-CPT; BRIEF-2; GARS-3S; SCQ; RBS-R; Sensory Profile-2	General Intelligence Index (RIAS): 91; Nonverbal IQ (TONI-4): 97; MOXO: severe impairment in attention and response time; BRIEF-2: clinically significant impairment in emotional and inhibitory control; GARS-3S: Index 81 (very likely ASD); SCQ: 10 (below cutoff); RBS-R: mild severity in repetitive behaviors	Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) level 1; attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD); significant difficulties in sensory processing

Nota. WPPSI-III: Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence; ADHD-5: ADHD Rating Scale-5; Sensory Profile-2: Sensory Profile 2; RIAS: Reynolds Intellectual Assessment Scales; TONI-4: Test of Nonverbal Intelligence; MOXO d-CPT: Continuous Performance Test; BRIEF-2: Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function; GARS-3S: Gilliam Autism Rating Scale; SCQ: Social Communication Questionnaire; RBS-R: Repetitive Behavior Scale–Revised.

Discussion

The present case documents the developmental trajectory of a male participant who, after presenting a regressive clinical phenotype at 18 months of age, showed an evolution consistent with functional remission following the application of a CNI. Functional remission (optimal outcome) [7] is defined here, in accordance with previous literature, as the loss of core diagnostic features and the normalization of daily functional performance.

Of particular scientific relevance is the episode of clinical fluctuation observed at 5 years of age. The documented clinical relapse occurred following systematic deviations from the dietary regimen, was associated with acute behavioral dysregulation (inflexibility and phenotypes consistent with ADHD), and resolved within four months after reinstatement of the biological intervention. This phenomenon is consistent with the Psychoneuroimmunoendocrinology (PNIE) framework and suggests that, in this neurodivergent profile, behavioral and executive alterations are highly dependent on the homeostasis of the gastrointestinal ecosystem. [9]

Furthermore, the documented acute episode holds significant methodological value, as it was evaluated under blinded conditions. In the absence of prior knowledge of the regressive autism history, the independent evaluating center identified only symptomatology consistent with ADHD and cognitive inflexibility, in the presence of above-average IQ (113). This divergence constitutes a quasi-experimental condition, providing unusual empirical evidence of diagnostic variability under blinded versus non-blinded clinical assessments. This objective finding documents the phenomenon known as diagnostic overshadowing [8], as well as the presence of successful functional masking mechanisms (masking).

This study presents limitations inherent to its single-case design, which preclude the establishment of causal relationships and limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, some of the measures used, particularly in the early phases, were based on parent-reported data, which are

susceptible to perception bias. Future research with prospective designs, larger samples, and standardized independent assessments will be necessary to confirm these findings.

Conclusions

The early application of a CNI in a case of severe regressive autism (initiated at 18 months of age) was associated with an accelerated clinical evolution consistent with functional remission (*optimal outcome*). After 24 months of active biological intervention and a subsequent rescue period, the participant achieved remission of core sociocommunicative deficits, transitioning toward a residual high-functioning neurodivergence characterized by ADHD, sensory processing alterations, and ASD level 1.

The acute episode of clinical fluctuation documented at 5 years of age, triggered by systematic deviations from the immunonutritional (trophological) regimen [9] and reversed within just 4 months after its reinstatement, suggests a potential causal dependence between the homeostasis of the biological terrain (gut–brain axis) and behavioral regulation in neurodevelopment.

Furthermore, the diagnostic contrast between independent external evaluations highlighted the phenotypic complexity of these cases: a blinded evaluation conducted at 5 years of age identified only ADHD and above-average intelligence (IQ 113) without detecting the autistic phenotype, documenting a clear phenomenon of diagnostic overshadowing [8] and the presence of successful functional masking mechanisms (masking). These findings suggest the transformative impact of multimodal naturopathic approaches with parental coaching [11] and underscore that functional remission is a dynamic process requiring long-term maintenance of biological stability.

Patient Perspective

“Our experience with the Katia Dolle Foundation program has been a transformative journey. Before starting, our son had experienced a profound regression: he stopped babbling, lost eye contact, and became socially withdrawn, developing hand flapping and hyperfocus.”

“After initiating dietary changes and natural supplementation, the improvements were remarkable. He overcame recurrent respiratory issues, regained functional language, began to develop symbolic play (‘playing doctor’) with peers, and showed a marked reduction in frustration.”

“At 5 years of age [...] we became lax with the dietary guidelines [...] We noticed severe emotional dysregulation, no tolerance to frustration, and social withdrawal. After resuming the strict approach, the dysregulation decreased significantly.”

“Now, at 7 years of age, he is a happy child who functions very well [...] actively participates in class and plays in an integrated way with groups of children [...] he is now able to verbally express what bothers him instead of reacting aggressively.”

“The Katia Dolle Method not only improved his health and quality of life, but also gave us hope and the tools to support him.”

Informed Consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate consent forms from the parents of the child included in this study. In these forms, the parents provided consent for the publication of information related to the case.

The parents understand that names and initials will not be published and that all reasonable efforts will be made to conceal the child’s identity, although anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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